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Integrated Farming System - An Ecofriendly Approach for Sustainable Agricultural Environment – A Review

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Research Article

Integrated Farming System - An Ecofriendly Approach for Sustainable Agricultural Environment – A Review

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable development in agriculture must include integrated farming system (IFS) with efficient soil, water crop and pest management practices, which are environmentally friendly and cost effective. In IFS, the waste of one enterprise becomes the input of another for making better use of resources. In integrated crop livestock farming system, crop residues can be used for animal feed, while manure from livestock can enhance agricultural productivity. IFS also play an important role in improving the soil health by increasing the nitrogen, phosphorous, organic carbon and microbial count of soil and thus, reduces the use of chemical fertilizers. Moreover, IFS components are known to control the weed and regarded as an important element of integrated pest management and thus minimizes the use of weed killers as well as pesticides and thus protects the environment. The water use efficiency and water quality of IFS was better than conventional system.

Keywords: IFS, Environment, Soil health, weed control, pest control.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of sustainability is an important element in the development of integrated systems. The MEA (2005) defined it as a characteristic or state whereby the needs of the present and local population can be met without compromising the ability of future generation or population in other locations to meet their needs. Developing countries around the world are promoting sustainable development through sustainable agricultural practices which will help them in addressing socioeconomic as well as environmental issues simultaneously. Within the broad concept of sustainable agriculture "Integrated Farming Systems (IFS)" hold special position as in this system nothing is wasted, the byproduct of one system becomes the input for other. Sustainable development in agriculture must include integrated farming system with efficient soil, water crop and pest management practices, which are environmentally friendly and cost effective. Integrated farming system are often less risky, if managed efficiently, they benefit from synergisms among enterprises, diversity produce environmental soundness (Lightfoot, 1990). Moreover, based on the principle of enhancing natural biological processes above and below the ground, the integrated system is the combination that reduces erosion, increases crop yields, soil biological activity and nutrient recycling, helps in efficient use of water, reduces pest and diseases, intensifies land use, improving profits and can therefore help reduce poverty and malnutrition and strengthen environmental sustainability.

INTEGRATED CROP LIVESTOCK FARMING SYSTEM

An integrated farming system consists of a range of resource-saving practices that aim to achieve acceptable profits and high and sustained production levels, while minimizing the negative effects of intensive farming and preserving the environment (Lal and Miller, 1990; Gupta et al., 2012). Within this framework, an integrated crop-livestock farming system represents a key solution for enhancing livestock production and safeguarding the environment through prudent and efficient resource use. In integrated crop livestock farming system the waste of one enterprise becomes the input of another for making better use of resources (Tiwari, 1993). For example, crop residues can be used for animal feed, while manure from livestock can enhance agricultural productivity by intensifying nutrients that improve soil fertility as well as reducing the use of chemical fertilizers (Gupta et al., 2012).

For agricultural use animal excreta can be used for fertilizer, feed and fuel. Excreta have two crucial roles in the overall sustainability of the system:

1. Improving nutrient cycling

Excreta contain several nutrients (including nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium) and organic matter, which are important for maintaining the soil structure and fertility. Animal excreta contains the major inorganic nutrient components (N, P and K) (Table1)

Table 1: Typical values for the nutrient content of manure sampled in Virginia. Values are in pounds of nutrient/ton except where noted for liquid sources

Total Nutrient Content (pounds/ton or pounds/1000 gallons)†			
Manure	Nitrogen	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O
Dry Broiler Litter	62.58	62.12	28.57
Dry Turkey Litter	61.75	63.68	24.36
Layer or Breeder	36.46	65.06	24.22
Liquid Dairy*	22.61	12.07	18.92
Semi-Solid Dairy	10.54	6.12	8.67
Semi-Solid Beef	12.79	6.67	11.30
Swine Lagoon*	10.14	5.68	5.72
Mixed Swine*	41.13	29.75	18.18

* Values are in pounds/1000 gallons. All other values are in pounds/ton.

Source: Mullins 2009

2. Providing energy

Excreta can be dried, composted, or liquid-composted for the production of biogas and energy for household use (e.g. cooking, lighting) or for rural industries (e.g. powering mills and water pumps). Fuel in the form of biogas or dung cakes can replace charcoal and wood. It can be methane-fermented, directly combusted, or made into solid fuel.

Furthermore biomass production of feed is possible; the excreta is treated to be used as feed again (Moriya and Kitagawa, 2007; Matsumoto and Matsuyama 1995).

However, increased amounts of manure must be treated, broken down into biologically safe and usable materials, and disposed in a safe way. Livestock manure treatment is generally accomplished by moving manure into either large manure-holding structures or earthen holding areas called lagoons. In the pond-like lagoons, bacteria break down the manure into two products: a clear water called effluent that can be drained off and a sludge that is generally applied to surrounding land (IAN, 1998).

Animal manure can be an important addition to help soil fertility and increase production, but excessive quantities may cause water and air pollution problems. But land application of manure to recycle nutrients can lead to an accumulation of soil nitrogen and phosphorus which in turn increases the potential for losses by runoff and leaching. Taking this into consideration, the following choices are possible to keep the environmental capacity in control:

- 1) Excreta cannot be discharged beyond the environmental capacity. Decrease the quantity of excreta to keep the capacity.
- 2) More excreta than the environmental capacity can be discharged. In that case, however, the excreta must be treated.

With regard to (1), because the quantity of excreta produced at a farm is the total of the excreta from each animal kept there, the measures are naturally suggested: (a) decrease the number of animals, or; (b) decrease the quantity of excreta per animal (per weight). However, as (b) is not supposed to be easy to carry out, (a) is the realistic measure. In order to reduce the number of animals and maintain the business at the same time, the value per animal needs to be enhanced. With regard to (2), the measure is to implement an actual excreta disposal method (Kawata, 2011).

Paddy Cum Fish Culture

The system of farming is most prevalent in Japan, China, Indonesia, India, Thailand and Philippines. Many reports suggest that integrated rice-fish farming is ecologically sound because fish improve soil fertility by increasing the availability of nitrogen and phosphorus (Giap et al., 2005, Dugan et al., 2006). On the other hand, rice fields provide fish with planktonic, periphytic and benthic food (Mustow, 2002).

In paddy cum fish culture the fish species selected for cultivation should have faster growth rate. Species such as *Catla catla*, *Labeo rohita*, *Cirrhinus mrigala*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Tilapia mossambicus*, *Anabas*, *Clarius batarchus* and *Channa* species were widely cultured in rice field (Shamsuddin, 2013). Table 2 shows the comparison between environmental requirements of rice and fish

Table 2: Comparison between environmental requirements of rice and fish

Parameter	Normal range	
	Rice	Fish
Depth of water	Minimum saturated soils with no flooding Ideal: Continuous flooding started at 3 cm depth gradually increasing to max of 15 cm by 60 th day. Complete draining 1-2 weeks before harvest (Singh et al 1980)	0.4 – 1.5 m for nursery and 0.8 to 3.0 m for grow out (Pillay 1990)
Temperature	Water and soil temperature of upto 40° C and fluctuations of upto 10° C in one day apparently with no deleterious effect.	25 ° C to 35 ° C for warm water species. Stable temperature preferable. Feeding may slow down at temperatures below or above normal range. Metabolic rate doubles almost
pH of water	Neutral to alkaline	6.5 to 9.0 (Boyd 1979)
Oxygen	Important during seedling stage for development of radicles	Preferably at near saturation or saturation level (5.0 to 7.5 ppm depending on temperature)
Ammonia	High levels of ammonia common immediately after fertilization	Un-ionized ammonia highly toxic. Ionised forms generally safe
Transparency or Turbidity	Immaterial	Important for growth of natural food. Very high level of suspended soil particles may impair respiration
Culture period	90-120 days for high yielding varieties, upto 160 days for traditional varieties	120-240 days depending upon species and market requirement.

ROLE OF IFS IN IMPROVING SOIL HEALTH AND NUTRIENT CYCLING

Soil health is declining in many cropping systems both in developed and developing countries (FAO, 2011). The ICRISAT (*International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics*) consortium team assessed 3622 soil samples from the farmers' fields in different states of India (Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat and Tamil Nadu) and observed widespread deficiencies of sulfur (S), zinc (Zn) and boron (B), along with total nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) (Sahrawat et al., 2008) (Table 3).

Table 3: Percentage of farmer's fields deficient in soil nutrients in different states of India

State	Org. C (%)	Nutrients (mg/kg soil)				
		Av.P	K	S	B	Zn
Andhra Pradesh	84	39	12	87	88	81
Karnataka	58	49	18	85	76	72
Madhya Pradesh	9	86	1	96	65	93
Rajasthan	22	40	9	64	43	24
Gujarat	12	60	10	46	100	82
Tamil Nadu	57	51	24	71	89	61
Kerala	11	21	7	96	100	18

IFS also play an important role in improving the soil health by increasing the nutritional value of soil. The benefits of the use of livestock manure in crop production are improvements in soil physical properties and the provision of N, P, K and other mineral nutrients. The application of livestock manure increases soil organic matter content, and this leads to improved water infiltration and water holding capacity as well as an increased cation exchange capacity. Manure and urine raise the pH level and accelerate the decomposition of organic matter and termite activity (Brouwer and Powell, 1995; 1998).

Channabasavanna et al. (2002) reported the changes in chemical properties of soil under rice-based farming systems (Table 4). The available N, P₂O₅ and K₂O contents of soil varied significantly. Maximum available N was recorded in rice (fish)-rice (fish) with poultry and minimum in rice-rice system. The maximum P₂O₅ was recorded in rice (GLM)-rice (GM) systems followed by rice (fish)-rice (fish) with poultry and rice-rice with dairy. The rice (fish) - rice (fish) with or without poultry recorded the highest available K₂O in soil.

Table 4: Soil nutrients as influenced by rice based farming systems

Treatment	N (kg/ha)	P ₂ O ₅ (kg /ha)	K ₂ O (kg /ha)
Rice-rice	256	41.2	556
Rice-sesame	336	42.9	725
Rice-chilli	396	43.1	676
Rice-wheat-GM	355	44.2	730
Rice+Fish(Ri)- Rice+Fish(dung)	410	43.9	704
Rice+Fish(Ri)+ Rice+Fish(poultry)- poultry	421	44.8	733
Rice+Fish(Ri)- Rice+Fish(fish feed)	373	44.0	701
Rice-rice-banana on bunds	286	42.1	626
Rice-rice-drumstick and curry leaf on bunds	270	41.9	634
Rice-rice-paragrass and cowpea on bunds+ dairy	385	44.7	705
Rice GLM- rice	397	45.0	695
Rice-rice-GM	385	44.2	680

Source: Channabasavanna et al., 2002

Channabasavanna and Biradar (2007) reported that nutritional status of soil N show increased trend from 187 kg/ ha to 362 kg/ha (40%) in rice-fish poultry system (Table 5). The increase was to the tune of 11.5% over conventional systems. Similarly, P and K content showed increased trend with IFS .

Table 5: Water requirement and NPK status after experimentation on IFS

Treatments	*Employment generation (man-days)	*Water requirement (ha.cm)	N (kg/ha) (187**)	P (kg/ha) (29.3)	K (kg/ha) (503)
Integrated farming system					
Rice-fish(pit at one side) and poultry (shed on fish pit)	600	375	250	32.8	490
Rice-fish(pit at one side connected by trenches) and poultry (shed on fish pit)	612	375	255	33.1	485
Rice-fish(pit at the centre) and poultry (reared separately)	625	352	275	33.5	530
Rice-fish(pit at one centre connected by trenches) and poultry (reared separately)	625	347	262	33.5	525
Rice-fish(pit at four corners connected by trenches) and poultry (reared separately)	628	360	269	33.6	510
Mean	618	362	362	33.3	508
Conventional cropping system					
Control(rice-rice system)	6,667	266	235	31.8	495

*Mean over two years, **Initial level

Source: Channabasavanna and Biradar, 2007

Solaiappan et al. (2007) examined different farming system models such as (A)Conventional cropping, (B)Crop+ poultry(20) + goat (4), (C)Crop+ poultry(20) + goat (4) +dairy (1), (D)Crop+ poultry(20) + goat (4) + sheep (6) and (E)Crop+ poultry(20) + goat (4) + sheep (6) + dairy (1) and found IFS model (E) recorded maximum organic carbon (0.35%), available soil N (134 kg / ha), soil P (8.5 kg/ha) and soil K (378kg/ha) at the end of study (Table 6).

Table 6: Available soil N, P and K (kg/ha) and organic C (%) at the start and completion of the study under different farming system models

Model	2003				2005				Increase %			
	N	P	K	Organic C	N	P	K	Organic C	N	P	K	Organic C
A	115	7.7	310	0.28	118	8.1	342	0.31	2.6	5.2	10.3	10.7
B	114	7.5	312	0.25	124	8.3	350	0.33	8.8	10.8	12.2	32.0
C	120	7.3	315	0.26	132	8.3	369	0.34	10.0	13.7	17.1	30.8
D	118	7.5	318	0.27	128	8.4	358	0.33	8.5	12.0	12.6	22.2
E	121	7.4	314	0.27	134	8.5	378	0.35	10.7	14.9	20.4	29.6
Mean	118	7.5	314	0.27	127	8.3	359	0.33	8.1		14.5	25.1

Source: Solaiappan et al., 2007

Nageswaran et al. (2009) studies the various soil parameters for comparing the IFS and CFS and found neutrality of pH was attained in IFS plot possibly due to intensive application of organic input while in CFS there was building up of salt leading to alkalinity. The concentration of organic carbon and population of microbes namely bacteria, actinomycetes and fungi in IFS have shown an increasing trend. All these parameters are actually indicators of good soil health (Table 7 and Table 8).

Table 7: Data on Soil pH and Organic carbon (%) at eight observation points between 1998 and 2002 in the IFS and two conventional farms.

Year	Soil pH			Organic Carbon (%)		
	IFS	CFS I	CFS II	IFS	CFS I	CFS II
Nov 98	7.80	7.60	7.92	0.54	0.65	0.60
Apr 99	7.50	7.84	8.26	0.52	0.41	0.42
Nov 99	7.69	7.89	7.95	0.93	0.71	0.58
Feb 00	7.82	7.95	7.21	0.65	0.50	0.50
Nov 00	7.68	8.13	8.19	0.93	0.75	0.89
Apr 01	7.68	8.28	8.31	0.65	0.50	0.50
Nov 01	7.80	7.80	7.80	1.04	0.62	0.85
Apr 02	7.00	7.40	7.50	1.18	0.54	0.59

Source: Nageswaran et al., 2009

Table 8: Microbial population (million) in the IFS and two conventional farms

	IFS	CFS I	CFS II
Bacteria THC(X 10 ⁵)	94	46	56
Actinomycetes CFU (X 10 ⁴)	42	6	15
Fungi CFFU(X 10 ³)	86	44	55

Source: Nageswaran et al., 2009

The rice fish prawn system of Mohanty et al. (2010) revealed the levels of organic carbon, available nitrogen and phosphorous in the soil showed significant higher increments in the deepwater rice-fish prawn system than in the rice monocarp system (Table 9). This may be attributed to additional nutrients from fish feed and faeces and fish grazing on the photosynthetic aquatic biomass and other components of the system which aids in nutrient recycling.

Table 9: Soil and water quality parameters in rice monocarp and rice-fish prawn systems

Parameter	Rice monocarp	Rice-fish prawn system
pH	7.52 (6.7-8.1)	7.31 (6.9-8.5)
Dissolved oxygen (ppm)	6.1 (4.4-8.9)	4.9(3.3-8.4)
Temperature (°C)	28.7 (27.9-31.5)	28.4 (27.3-31.4)
Total alkalinity(ppm)	83 (73-107)	94 (68-109)
Dissolved organic matter (ppm)	2.6 (0.55-3.6)	3.4 (1.45-4.8)
TSS (ppm)	177 (60-257)	225 (132-297)
NH ⁴⁺ water (ppm)	0.59 (0.41-0.91)	0.68 (0.34-0.97)
Chlorophyll a (mg/m ³)	22.3 (18.8-31.3)	41.1 (21.1-62.2)
Total plankton (units/l)	7.3 X 10 ³ (9.4 X 10 ² - 1.8 X 10 ⁴)	3.3 X 10 ⁴ (2.9 X 10 ³ - 6.7 X 10 ⁴)
Nitrite – N (ppm)	0.033 (0.011-0.07)	0.037 (0.012-0.072)
Nitrate- N (ppm)	0.36(0.16-0.61)	0.37 (0.05-0.49)
Phosphate (ppm)	0.26 (0.13-0.54)	0.21 (0.06-0.33)
Available N in soil (mg 100/g)	19.3 (20.1-21.9)	20.3 (17.9-21.6)
Avalibale P in soil (mg 100/g)	2.11 (1.63-2.89)	2.23 (1.28-2.93)
Organic carbon in soil (%)	0.62 (0.57-0.75)	0.66 (0.49-0.82)
Soil pH	6.94 (6.6-7.1)	7.01 (6.8-7.1)

Values in parentheses represent range

Source: Mohanty et al., 2010

ROLE OF IFS COMPONENTS IN WEED AND PEST CONTROL

One problem in agricultural environment is related to the use of some pesticides (Turrall and Burke, 2010). Pest and weed management has been a recurrent issue in irrigated agriculture since the emergence of modern large-scale rice and wheat farming. In monocultures, pests and diseases can spread rapidly and result in epidemics when conditions are favourable to a particular pathogen or pest. Some high-yielding varieties of rice have proved to be susceptible to particular pests (e.g. IR64 to brown plant hopper). Agricultural run-off and drainage readily transport the pesticide pollutants to water bodies and causing a great harm.

Conventional cropping systems in the Central USA have low levels of biological diversity and rely heavily on synthetic fertilizers and herbicides. These are common contaminants of waterways and cause environmental degradation. Ecological theory suggests that diversified cropping systems integrated with livestock should have a reduced reliance on chemicals and fertilizers and should lower production costs and environmental pollution (Liebman, 2008).

Network trails conducted at various sites in France revealed that amount of herbicides, insecticides, chemical fertilizers and fungicides used in IFS compared with Conventional Farming System (CFS) decreased by 10.1, 28.3, 41.3 and 89.8 percent respectively (Table 10).

Table 10: Reduction of inputs at Saint-Hilaire (1991-95) and reduction of wheat yields at Boigneville (1991-94) for Integrated Farming Systems compared with Conventional Farming Systems

Saint- Hilaire (1991-95) Input Reduction (%)	Boigneville (1991-94) Yield reduction (%)
Seed (+2.6)	1991(-34.6)
Herbicide (-10.1)	1992(-19.6)
Insecticide (-28.3)	1993(-15.9)
Fertilizer(-41.3)	1994(-14.8)
Fungicide (-89.8)	Mean(-21.2)

Compared with using herbicides, which need protective measures to minimize contamination, the use of animals is safer for the farmer and the environment. In Malaysia, the use of sheep for weed control has been a practical and important method for the expansion of sheep production in the country, which has increased the returns per unit area of land (Devendra and Thomas, 2002).

Long term effects of integrating fish and poultry components with rice have been studied by Kathiresan (2007) which indicated that fish and poultry components independently contributed for 26 and 24% weed control respectively and fish + poultry together contributed for 30% weed control. The same study also proved that application of sugar factory bi-product presumed as organic manure with dual culturing of bio-fertilizer *Azolla* in the integrated rice + fish + poultry farming system could offer 69% weed control, paving then way to dispense with herbicide application (Gunasekaran and Kathiresan, 2003).

Kathiresan (2009) reported that the herbivores fish species viz. grass carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*), Tilapia sp. (*Sarotherodon niloticus*) and Common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) contributing for significantly higher biomass reduction in the three weed species viz. 33.17% of *Echinochloa sp.*; 31.82% of *Cyperus rotundus* and 28.75% of *Eclipta alba* in rice-fish integrated farming system (Table 11). Kathiresan (2009) found that grazing by goats in the off-season reduced weed infestation in millets during the cropping season through their feeding habits but addition of fresh goat manure slightly brought down weed control by virtue of effect by favouring higher weed counts and biomass especially with annuals, compared to grazing alone (Table 12). This is attributed to re-infestation by annual weed seeds through the goat manure by virtue of the process of endozoochory. However, the total weed count and weed biomass in the treatments involving goat manure addition were significantly lesser than the untreated control. This weed control might be due to reduced soil pH and reduced recuperation of soil weed bank. Goat rearing, when integrated as a farming component in dry lands where millet was grown during cropping season, supplemented weed control and reduced weed infestation, significantly by imparting weed control indices of 17.7% and 31.34% during the first and second year respectively. Excluding goat manure addition, grazing alone supplemented weed control in millets recording weed control indices of 25.20% and 45.17% respectively (Geetha et al., 2005). This could be appreciated from higher grain yields in goat grazing alone compared to treatments involving goat grazing + goat manuring. It could be suggested that instead of adding fresh manure to the field, allowing the goat manure to decompose throughout the offseason and incorporating it in the field just before raising the crop, could yield better results in terms of reducing weed competition and favouring millet yields.

Table 11: Percentage reduction in biomass of weeds in rice fish integrated farming system

Fish species	<i>Echinochloa sp.</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	<i>Eclipta alba</i>
Grass carp	33.17	31.82	28.75
Tilapia	15.48	14.00	14.59
Common carp	22.37	20.86	18.00
Grass carp and Tilapia	21.02	19.80	16.73
Grass Carp and common carp	28.13	25.18	22.78
Tilapia and common carp	20.46	18.74	16.01
Grass carp, Tilapia and common carp	23.65	0.86	21.71

Source: Kathiresan, 2009

Table 12: Effect of grazing on weeds in IFS

Treatment	Weed biomass (g/m ²)		Weed control index (%)	
	2003	2004	2003	2004
Control	83.90	62.25	-	-
Goat grazing	62.76	34.13	25.20	45.17
Penning	74.45	42.74	11.26	32.95
Grazing and penning	69.04	39.75	17.70	31.34
CD (P=0.05)	6.09	4.92	-	-

Source: Kathiresan, 2009

Integrated rice-fish farming is also being regarded as an important element of integrated pest management (IPM) in rice crops (Berg, 2001, Halwart and Gupta, 2004). Fish play a significant role in controlling aquatic weeds and algae that carry diseases, act as hosts for pests and compete with rice for nutrients. Moreover, fish eat flies, snails and insects, and can help to control malaria mosquitoes and water-borne diseases (Matteson, 2000). Interactions of fish and rice also help lower production costs because insects and pests are consumed by the fish. The bio-control of rice pests is one of the prominent features of rice-fish farming which further minimize the use of pesticides for production of rice crop.

Bingyou et al. (2001) and Zhonghua (1996) based on their results, found that fish could play an effective role as a bio-control agent against rice pests and diseases as showed in Table 13 and Table 14 respectively.

Table 13: The effect of bio-control of rice pests and diseases in rice-fish ecosystems

Treatment	Rice plant hopper	<i>Naranga aenescens</i>	Moore <i>Parnara guttata</i> Bremer & Grey	Rice leaf roller	Rice leaf hopper	Sheath rot (%)
Rice monoculture	237	534	20	11	839	37.7
Rice fish system	75	107	10	6	227	4.9

Source: Bingyou et al. (2001)

Table 14: The incidence of rice pests, rice diseases and weeds in rice-fish system

Treatment	Rice plant hopper	Rice blast (%)	Sheath rot (%)	Quantity of weeds (numbers/m ²)	Biomass of weeds (g/m ²)
Rice monoculture	8.3	51.3	20.9	46-50	420-460
Rice fish system	2.7	27.4	6.7	0	0

Source: Zhonghua (1996)

WATER USE EFFICIENCY AND WATER QUALITY IN IFS

Agriculture is the largest consumer of water in world. The quantity of water available to agriculture is likely to be affected by dwindling of the groundwater resource in many areas. Widespread and largely unregulated groundwater withdrawals by agriculture have resulted in depletion and degradation of some of the world's most accessible and high-quality aquifers and such areas include Punjab, North China Plain and the Souss basin in Morocco, where annual declines of up to 2 metres since 1980 have been recorded (Garduno and Foster, 2011). Due to demand of water for industrial and drinking purposes, the share of available water resources in agriculture sector is reducing substantially in near future. IFS results in multiple uses of water for higher productivity and future strategies for enhancing water productivity (Behera et al., 2012).

Rice itself is a water consuming crop. Addition of fish still increased the water requirement. Channabasavanna and Biradar (2007) reported that IFS consumed 36% higher water than the conventional system of rice-rice but the water use efficiency was 71% higher in IFS than conventional system (Table 4). Earlier, Jayanthi et al. (2000) indicated that integrated farming requires less water per unit of production than mono-cropping systems. Channabasavanna et al. (2009) also reported that integrated farming system requires only 1247 mm of water and on the other hand conventional farming system requires 2370 mm of water.

The various agricultural activities involved have far reaching impacts upon the hydrological cycle due to high usage of pesticides and fertilizers. Oksel et al. (2009) carried out the studies to determine the impacts of integrated farming towards Langgas River water quality. From the overall finding, the study indicated that integrated farming affected Langgas River water quality but in the value is still within the acceptable limit. From the mean concentration results, Langgas River is free from organic contamination. Four different sampling points were chosen which consisted of upper part of Langgas River; consisted of clear water flowing over series of shallow gravel riffles (Station 1), downstream of Langgas River which is border of the estate (Station 2), middle of Langgas River (Station 3) and Madai Waterfall as the baseline point (Station 4). A total of ten water quality parameters were studied which consisted of phosphate, ammonia-nitrogen, biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), turbidity, temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, conductivity and total suspended solid (TSS). Four sampling points were selected within Langgas River which is associated with integrated farming activity which consist of upstream, downstream, middle and Madai Waterfall (baseline station). Mean concentrations of water quality are summarized in Table 15. With regards to Malaysian Interim Water Quality Standard (INWQS), indicates that Langgas River still has good water quality.

Table 15: Mean water Quality concentrations associated with integrated farming activity

Parameters	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3	Station 4
Phosphate (mg/L)	0.55	0.67	0.64	0.85
Ammonianitrogen (mg/L)	0.01	0	0.05	0.06
BOD (mg/L)	0.56	0.69	0.57	0.65
COD (mg/L)	0.67	4.33	3.33	2.10
Turbidity (NTU)	2.82	1.50	20.8	20.3
Temperature (°C)	28.0	27.5	27.2	28.62
DO (mg/L)	6.81	5.86	4.11	7.05
pH	8.10	8.44	7.71	8.21
Conductivity (mS/cm)	0.56	0.54	0.63	0.31
TSS (mg/L)	4.3	3.57	17.8	17.4

Source: Oksel et al., 2009

CONCLUSION

IFS is also an eco - friendly approach in which waste of one enterprise becomes the input of another thus making efficient use of resources. It helps in improving the soil health, weed and pest control, increase water use efficiency and maintains water quality. As this system minimizes the use of harmful chemical fertilizers, weed killers and pesticides and thus safeguards the environment from the adverse effects.

REFERENCES

- Behera, U. K. , Panigraha, P. and Sarangi, A. (2012). Multiple Water Use Protocols in Integrated Farming System for Enhancing Productivity . *Water Resource Management* , 26:2605-2623.
- Berg, H. (2001). Pesticide use in rice and rice-fish farms in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam. *Crop Protection*, 20: 897–905.
- Bingyou, L., Wang, Rusong, Zhang and Renwu , (2001). Relationship between populations diversity and its micro-environments in farmland ecosystem — evaluation for diversity of several farmlands ecosystems. *Chinese Journal of Ecology*, 20 (2): 5–7.
- Boyd, C.E. (1979). Water quality in warmwater fish ponds. Auburn University Agricultural Experiment Station, pp. 359.
- Brouwer, J. and Powell, J.M. (1998). Micro-topography, water balance, millet yield and nutrient leaching in a manuring experiment on sandy soil in south-west Niger. In: Renard, G., Neef, A., Becker, K. and Von Oppen, M. (Eds), *Soil fertility management in West African land use systems*. Proc. of a workshop held in Niamey, 4-8 March 1997. Margraf, Weikersheim, pp. 349-360.
- Brouwer, J. and Powell, J.M. (1995). Soil aspects of nutrient cycling in a manure experiment in Niger. In: Powell, J.M., Fernandez-Rivera, S., Williams, T.O. and Renard, C. (Eds.). *Livestock and sustainable nutrient cycling in mixed farming systems of sub-Saharan Africa*. Vol II: Technical papers. Proc. of an International Conference held in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 22.-26. November 1993. ILCA, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, pp. 211-226.
- Channabasavanna, A.S. and Biradar, D.P. (2007). Rice-fish poultry system model for rice growing farmers of Karnataka. *Indian farming*, 57 (5): 20-22.
- Channabasavanna, A.S., Biradar, D.P., Prabhudev, K.N. and Hegde, M. (2009). Development of profitable integrated farming system model for small and medium farmers of Tungabhadra project area of Karnataka. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 22(1): 25-27.
- Channabasavanna, A.S., Itnal, C.J. and Patil, S.G. (2002). Productivity, economic analysis and changes in physico-chemical properties of soil as influenced by integrated rice (*Oryza sativa*) based farming systems. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*. 47(1): 1-5.
- Devendra C and Thomas D (2002). Crop animal interactions in mixed farming systems in Asia. *Agricultural Systems*, 7: 27-40.
- Dugan, P., Dey, M.M. and Sugunan, V.V. (2006). Fisheries and water productivity in tropical river basins: enhancing food security and livelihoods by managing water for fish. *Agricultural Water Management*, 80: 262-275.
- FAO, (2011). *The state of the world's land and water resources for food and agriculture (SOLAW) – Managing systems at risk*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome and Earthscan, London. pp 285.
- Garduno, H. and Foster, S. (2011). *Sustainable groundwater irrigation: approaches to reconciling demand with resources*. GWMate Strategic Overview Series No. 4. Washington, DC, World Bank.
- Geetha, J., Kuttibai, T. and Kathiresan, R.M. (2005). Goat grazing for perennial weed control in rainfed agriculture. In: *Proc. Asian Pacific Weed Science Conference*. Vietnam. p. 483.
- Giap, D. H., Yi, Y. and Lin, C. K. (2005). Effects of different fertilization and feeding regimes on the production of integrated farming of rice and prawn *Macrobrachium rosenbergii* (De Man). *Aquaculture Research*, 36: 292–299.
- Gunasekaran, A.S. and Kathiresan, R.M. (2003). Integrated weed management in rice+fish+poultry farming system. In: *Proc. 19th Asian-Pacific Weed Science Society Conference*, Manila, Philippines. p. 115-121.
- Gupta, V., Rai, P.K. and Risam, K.S. (2012). Integrated Crop-Livestock Farming Systems: A Strategy for Resource Conservation and Environmental Sustainability. *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education*, Special Issue, 2: 49-54.
- Halwart, M. and Gupta, M.V. (2004). Culture of fish in rice fields. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and the World Fish Center, pp 83.
- IAN (1998). *The Iowa Association of Naturalists (IAN) :The Iowa Environmental Issues Series, REAP Conservation Education Board*, Iowa.
- Jayanthi, C., Rangasamy, A. and Chinnusamy, C. (2000). Water budgeting for components in lowland integrated farming systems. *Agricultural Journal*, 87(7/9): 411- 414.

- Kathiresan, R.M. (2007). Integration of elements of a farming system for a sustainable need and pest management in the tropics. *Crop Protection*, 26: 424-429.
- Kathiresan, R.M. (2009). Integrated farm management for linking environment. *Indian Journal of Agronomy* 54(1): 9-14.
- Kawata, Y. (2011). Pollution and Environmental Issues in Agriculture and the Livestock Industry: A Brief Review of the Japanese Case. <http://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/30277/>
- Lal, R. and Miller, F.P. (1990). Sustainable farming for tropics. In: Singh, R.P. (Ed.) *Sustainable agriculture: Issues and Prospective*. Vol.1 , pp. 69-89, Indian Society of Agronomy, IARI, New Delhi.
- Liebman, M., Gibson, L.R., Sundberg, D.N., Heggenstaller, A.H., Westman, P.R., Chase, C.A., Hartzler, R.G., Menalled, F.D, Davis, A.S. and Dixon, P.M. (2008). Agronomic, environmental, economic, and energetic characteristics of conventional and low-external-input cropping systems in the U.S Corn Belt. *Agronomy Journal*, 100: 600-610.
- Lightfoot, C. (1990). Integration of aquaculture and agriculture: a route to sustainable farming systems. *NAGA:The ICLARM Quarterly*, 13(1): 9-12.
- Matsumoto, H. and Matsuyama, S. (Ed.). (1995). *Livestock hygiene*. Japan Agricultural Development and Extension Association, Japan.
- Matteson, P.C. (2000). Insect-pest management in tropical Asian irrigated rice fields. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 5: 549–574.
- MEA (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment) (2005). Current State and trends (Eds. Hassan, R., Scholes, R. and Ash, N.) 1:133-134.
- Mohanty, R.K., Thakur, A.K., Ghosh, S. and Patil, D.U. (2010). Impact of rice fish prawn culture on rice field ecology and productivity. *Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 80: 597-602.
- Moriya, K., and Kitagawa, M. (2007). Old and new near-future style agricultural production. In: Imai, H. (Ed.) *New challenges in livestock production* , Kyoto University Press. pp. 217-244.
- Mullins, G. (2009) *Phosphorus, Agriculture and The Environment*. Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Petersburg.
- Mustow, S.E. (2002). The effects of shading on phytoplankton photosynthesis in rice-fish fields in Bangladesh. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 90: 89-96.
- Oksel, O., Razali, N., Yusoff, M.K., Ismail, M.Z., Pa'ee, K.F. and Ibrahim, K.N. (2009). The impacts of integrated farming to water quality: case study on Langgas River, Kunak, Sabah, Malaysia. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9: 341-346.
- Pillay, T.V.R. (1990). *Aquaculture principles and practices*. Fishing News Books, Oxford, England U.K., pp. 575.
- Sahrawat, K.L., Rego, T.J., Wani, S.P. and Pardhasaradhi, G. (2008). Stretching soil sampling to watershed: evaluation of soil test parameters in a semi-arid tropical watershed. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 39: 2950–2960.
- Singh, V.P., Early, A.C. and Wickham, T.H. (1980). Rice agronomy in relation to fish culture, p. 15-34. In: Pullin, R.S.V. and Shehadeh, Z.H. (Eds.) *Proc. of the ICLARMSEARCA Conf. on Integrated Agriculture-Aquaculture Farming Systems*, 6-9 August 1979, Manila, Philippines, pp. 258.
- Solaiappan, U., Subramanian, V. and Maruthi, G.R. (2007). Selection of suitable integrated farming system model for rain-fed semi-arid vertic inceptisols in Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, 52(3): 194-197.
- Tiwari, P.N. (1993). Integrated Farming Research for sustaining food production. *Journal of Nuclear Agriculture Biology*, 20 : 1-13.
- Turrall, H. and Burke, J. (2010). *Sustainable crop production and intensification in irrigated cropping systems*. Land and Water Division, FAO, Rome
- Zhonghua, L. (1996). Technology and benefits of controlled paddy field. *Journal of Soil and Fertilizer*, 4: 37–41.
- Shamsuddin, M. (2013). <http://www.scholar-park.com/index.php/fisheries/aquaculture/integrated-aquaculture/paddy-cum-fish-culture>